

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS BELONG TO BIOLOGICAL HOME AND SATRA IN THE DISTRICT OF MAJULI, ASSAM

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Abstract:

The ability which helps an individual to identify and manage his own emotions as well as of others is called emotional intelligence. It is one of the most potent regulating and directing forces of behavior. Emotions can run wild and bring havoc into one's life. 'Emotional atyachar' can make one's life unbearable while the other part of it is very much positive. Due to lack of emotional intelligence an individual can do any sort of unexpected anti-social activities. The success and failure in an examination is also greatly determined by E.Q. The purpose of the present study is to find out the emotional intelligence level among the secondary school students in general and the difference in their emotional intelligence level between the students groups residing at biological homes and in Satras in particular. The sample for the present study comprised of total 60 respondents: thirty (30) adolescents from Satras, and an equivalent number of students from biological family of Majuli district, Assam. Emotional intelligence level of the respondents has been assessed by using a standardized Emotional Intelligence Inventory (EII) developed by Dr. S.K. Mangal and Subhra Mangal. In the present study, it is observed that most of the students staying at satra and biological families exhibited poor level of emotional intelligence. Significant difference found between the respondents staying at Satra and Biological families with regard to level of emotional intelligence.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Satras and Biological Family.

Introduction:

Human beings are emotionally intelligent and intelligence is dependent on various factors such as heredity and environment, culture, health and physical development, and socio-economic condition. Emotions refer to love, happiness, affection, anger, sadness, surprise, fear, disgust etc. Through emotional behaviour usually, people try to convey their internal behaviors that how much he is happy or sad. The most precious gift of the almighty God to us is life. This life starts with growth, development and learning. But the rate of growth, development and learning may vary from man to man even from stage to stage of development. However, adolescence is a period when this growth, development as well as learning are believed to be at its pinnacle, since it is the period of transition of a child into an adult. This period is the most crucial stage and the later life of an individual is determined by this stage.

Secondary school students are in the very transitional stage. They start this stage of life with biology and ends in society (Peterson -1988). They have to perform a series of psycho-social

tasks for a separation from parents and family, coping with bodily changes, building their own values and norms, and increasing their financial and vocational skills. Thus, adolescence is a period of dramatic challenge as because they are to adjust to the various changes in the self, in the peer group, and even in the family. Psychologist Stanly Hall said, adolescence is a period of storm and stress. Obstacles in the development of emotion cannot build a sound personality. Emotions like love, anger, fear, disgust etc. have a profound role in the formation of personality. Not only his physical growth and development are linked with his emotional makeup but his intellectual, social, moral, and aesthetic development is also controlled by his emotional behavior and experiences.

The emotional balance is disturbed to students at secondary level. With regard to emotional experiences, this is the period of intensive storm and stress. At no stage, this emotional energy is as strong and dangerous as in adolescence. It is very difficult for a secondary school students to exercise control over his emotions. The sudden functioning of sexual glands and tremendous increase in physical energy makes him restless. Moreover, adolescents are not consistent in their emotions. Quick and frequent fluctuation of emotions is the attribute at this stage and which makes them moody. Sometimes they are very happy and at another time they are extremely and all this happens in a very short time. So there is too much uncertainty in the nature of their emotional states.

Emotional maladjustments and mental troubles are strong factors in the academic career of a student. Emotional problems of inferiority, jealousy and being thwarted are very common among the adolescents. Healy and Bronner in their study of 143 delinquents found that 92% of them revealed emotional disturbances. It is reported that in America about two third of Juvenile delinquents suffer from emotional personality and mental deviations. In India the rate of delinquency cases are also increasing day after day which is also not detrimental even in the state of Assam.

Emotional intelligence is the ability to identify and manage one's emotions as well as that of others. Emotional intelligence is measured in terms of E.Q. which includes three set of skills namely- emotional awareness, harnessing emotions for positive thinking and problem-solving, Inter personal or Intrapersonal skills.

Emotional intelligence (EI) is the capacity to understand and manage emotion; however, the content of this construct remain unsettled. **Mayer and Salovey**, the who originally used the term defined emotional intelligence as the ability to perceive emotion, integrate emotion to facilitate thought, understand emotions and to regulate emotions to promote personal growth. In the words of **Daniel Goleman**, Emotional intelligence is the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves and for managing emotions well, in ourselves and in our relationships. The findings of the researches done in earlier showed that Emotional Intelligence abilities were four times more important than I.Q. in determining professional success and prestige. Training and nurturing the emotions right from childhood is the utmost need of the hour so that they can develop mutual emotional understanding and lead a happy and prosperous life in the future (**Cherniss**).

The factors mentioned by **Daniel Goleman** help individual's functions effectively on a daily basis and in this respect emotional intelligence can be conceptualized as a person's success oriented traits. The constructs of emotional intelligence has immense value as it provides a framework to understand how emotional states affect social functioning, and it may have a predictive value above and beyond that of cognitive intelligence with regard to real life outcomes. E.L. Thorndike, who talk emotional intelligence as social intelligence, defined emotional intelligence as ability to understand and manage men and women, boys and girls to act wisely in human relations.

Emotional intelligence is deeply related to aggression and offending. The research finding demonstrate that persons with high levels of E.Q are more able to moderate their emotions and are less impulsive. On the other hand, individuals with low E.Q. are more prone to risky behavior. The adolescents who have the tendency of delinquency possess low level E.Q. Emotional insecurity is an another notable reasons of delinquency. The broken homes and families, lack of parental affection and security, absence of loving mother or an affectionate mother substitute, lack of family ties, desertion and separation are all contributory factors for low emotional intelligence in one hand and delinquency in the other. Moreover, a significant relationship exist between E.Q and academic achievement.

Area of the study: The present study was undertaken in Majuli District, the first river island district of India, situated in the Brahmaputra River in Northern Assam. On June 27, 2016, the then Chief Minister of Assam Sarbananda Sonwoal announced this new district constituting a population of 1, 67, and 304. The Majuli District, Assam has located at 27.901381 latitudes and 95.726033 longitudes.

Significance of the study- Emotions are the true regulating force of one's life. What does not happen due to emotion? The Romeo and Juliet, the Tajmahal in the memory of Mumtaz Mahal, the historical war etc. are the witnesses of emotions. Emotional intelligence always exist behind the screen in each success as well as failure. The emotions of the secondary school students are in the formative stage and if not reared and cared for properly they may confront problems in later life. So, identification and exploration of their emotional intelligence level is utmost importance. It is also becoming the need of the hour to know which one is the better effective environment for rearing a child in a religious or a family environment. If emotional intelligence skills are developed, strengthened and enhanced, students may demonstrate increased level of personal, academic and career achievement (**Vela, 2003**). The value of emotional intelligence can't be denied in scholastic achievement or maintaining a happy life. Therefore measuring the level of emotional intelligence among the secondary school students in two different family setting is becoming the need of the hour.

Operational Definitions:

Emotional Intelligence- Ability to know, understand and manage emotions of own as well as of others.

Satras- Satras, founded by Sri Sri Srimanta Sankardeva, are the religious institutional centers closely associated with the Ekasarana tradition of Vaishnavism. These independent religious

institutions are largely found in the world's largest river island Majuli of Assam and its neighboring regions. Satras are running under the control of individual adhikaras (or satradhikars).

Biological Home- Children who are being reared and cared for under the lap and supervision of parents.

Objectives of the study: The present study was undertaken with the following objectives:

1. To study the level of emotional intelligence of secondary school students being reared up in biological family and satra.
2. To make a comparative study of emotional intelligence level among the secondary school students being reared at satra and biological family.

Hypotheses of the study- The following hypotheses were set for the present study-

1. The level of emotional intelligence of secondary school students staying at Satra's are more than their counterpart.
2. There is no significant difference in the level of emotional intelligence of secondary school students staying at Satra and biological family.

Delimitations of the study- 1..It has studied only emotional intelligence of secondary school students who pursued secondary education under Board of Secondary Education, Assam (SEBA) in the district of Majuli.

2. The study is confined to family settings only.
3. The results found from this study can't be applied on other levels of education.

Population & Sample: All the secondary school students pursuing secondary courses in different subjects at various high schools in the district of Majuli, Assam, were considered as population. A sample of thirty (30) students, residing at Satra, and an equivalent number of students belongs to biological homes were purposively selected for the present study. A total sixty (60) respondents finally selected for the present study.

Tool: To collect the relevant data for the present study the standardized Emotional Intelligence Inventory (EII) developed by Dr. S.K. Mangal and Subhra Mangal has been used. It contains 100 items, 25 each from the four areas or aspects of EI namely intrapersonal awareness (knowing about one's own emotion), interpersonal awareness (knowing about other's emotion), intrapersonal management (managing one's own emotion), and interpersonal management (managing others emotion). The subject has to respond either "yes" or "no" in each item. Reliability of test is 0.92(Test Re- test method) and validity of this test is 0.71 from the inter validity formula.

Techniques used for data analysis and interpretation: The quantitative techniques were used for analysis and interpretation of collected data.

Statistical treatment: The simple percentage, mean, SD and t test techniques were used for analysis and interpretation of collected data.

Quantitative Analysis:

H1: The level of emotional intelligence of secondary school students staying at Satra’s are more than their counterpart.

Figure1: Line graph showing the level of Emotional Intelligence among secondary school students rearing in two different family environments.

Table: 1 Level of Emotional Intelligence among secondary school students.

	N	Level of Emotional Intelligence				
		Very Good	Good	Average	Poor	Very Poor
No..of respondents	60	Nil	5	19	30	6
Percentage.		Nil	8.33%	31.67%	50%	10%

Figure 1 and table 1 clearly shows that half of the total respondents i.e. 50% have showed poor level of emotional intelligence. A total of 31.67% respondents shown average level of emotional intelligence and 10% respondents shown very poor level emotional intelligence and only 8.33% respondents showed good level of emotional intelligence. Significantly not a single respondent has exposed very good level of emotional intelligence.

Figure 2: Pie diagram showing family setting wise the level of emotional intelligence.

Table 2: Family setting wise level of Emotional Intelligence among secondary school students rearing in two different family environments.

Family setting	N	M	Level of Emotional Intelligence				
			Very Good	Good	Average	Poor	Very Poor
Biological family	30	58.37	0%	0%	3.33%	76.66%	20%
Satra	30	57.25	0%	16.67%	60%	23.33%	0%

From the figure 2 and table 2, it has been observed that not a single respondent belonging to the biological family or Satra has exposed the very good level of emotional intelligence. A total of 60% of respondents belonging to Satra exposed the average level of emotional intelligence which was much higher than their counterparts. The highest number of respondents i.e. 76.66% belonging to biological family exposed the poor level of emotional intelligence and only 23.3% of respondents belonging to Satra showed the poor level of emotional intelligence. Moreover, 20% of respondents from biological families have shown very poor levels of emotional intelligence. Significantly majority of respondents belonging to biological families showed below-average levels of emotional intelligence.

Ho: There is no significant difference in the level of emotional intelligence of secondary school students staying at Satra's and biological family.

Table 3: Comparison of Emotional intelligence level among respondents belongs to Satra and Biological family.

Dimensions of E.I	Category	N	M	SD	df	t value	CR at % Level	Remarks
Intra personal Awareness	Satra	30	16.6	3.24	58	0.06	2.01	Insignificant
	Biological Family	30	15	3.11				
Inter personal Awareness	Satra	30	16.67	2.77	58	0.01	2.01	Insignificant
	Biological Family	30	14.67	2.89				
Intra personal Management	Satra	30	16.6	3.09	58	0.01	2.01	Insignificant
	Biological Family	30	13.8	3.74				
Inter personal Management	Satra	30	17.4	3.24	58	1.14	2.01	Insignificant
	Biological Family	30	13.9	2.32				
Emotional Intelligence in total	Satra	30	67.26	8.14	58	2.82	2.01	Significant
	Biological Family	30	57.37	6.56				

A close perusal of Table 3 shows that there is mean difference in the total level of emotional intelligence among the secondary school students belongs to satra and biological families. The comparative analysis of mean score among the respondents indicates that the difference is quite significant. The 't' value obtained while comparing the emotional intelligence level of the adolescents belongs to satra and biological families are significant at 5% significant level ($t=2.82 > 0.5$). Therefore, it can be said that there is significant difference in the level of emotional intelligence between the secondary school students who were residing at satra and biological families.

Suggestions to improve Emotional Intelligence among secondary school students:

1. Make involve the students in NSS, NCC or other social activities that will help them in getting their minds off of the personal problems at hand.
2. Develop the habit of reading books, going for a walk and helping parents with their domestic work.

3. Teach the students to use excessive use of sense organs for self-soothe during the time of distress.
4. Provisions of prayer to the Almighty God should be both at home and school. This prayer practice will teach them to surrender their problems to the God and thereby tolerance capacity of the students will develop.
5. Teach them to engage in different relaxing activities like- deep breathing, yoga, a relaxing walk to calm the psychological distress.
6. Developing the capacity among the learners to stay in the moment by letting go of the past and the future will help their emotions from overwhelming.
7. Teach the students to let go of attempts to control their emotions and learn that emotions themselves can't harm them.

Conclusion:

The destiny and development of a nation depend on the competent generation and to become it every student must possess a satisfactory level of emotional intelligence. Increasing the level of Emotional intelligence can build the broken warp and woof of life. The two basic keys of the teaching-learning process are attention and concentration as these assist in developing cognitive intelligence and make it easier to memorize the learned knowledge (Cross, 1974). Students having high EQ can keep their minds cool so they can easily absorb of information received and finally rise their academic achievement. Maria (2004) indicates that there is positive relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance. Teaching plans, adequate teaching aids, and human resources cannot lonely build the future guardians of the nation if they are unable to identify their self-emotions. Lack of emotional intelligence becomes a stumbling on the ladder of success (Azizi Yahaya et al.2012). Therefore, it is the need of the hour for the teaching community to put all their efforts, inside or outside the fence of the schools, to develop the level of emotional intelligence among the learners so that they can cope with the changing demands, and with a view to building a resilient and capable human face of globalization.

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